

Personality Traits, Coping Skills, and Self-Efficacy Among College Students of Laguna State Polytechnic University System Amid Pandemic

Dhon Jheriko B. Enrico*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study concentrated on the predictive nature of personality traits toward coping skills and self-efficacy among the students of Laguna State Polytechnic University System from different colleges in Santa Cruz, Siniloan, San Pablo City, and Los Baños Campuses (n = 1039) amid the COVID-19 pandemic. They responded to three adopted questionnaires: the Big Five Inventory for personality traits, the Brief COPE for coping skills, and the New General Self-Efficacy Scale for self-efficacy. Through multiple linear regression analysis, personality traits significantly explained the 28.2% variance in self-efficacy; as well as for every coping skill of the respondents: 22.9 % in problem-focused coping, 17.2 % in emotion-focused coping, and 19.8% in dysfunctional coping. Specifically, personality traits significantly explained the variance in the three coping skills: in problem-focused coping, all of the personality traits; in emotion-focused coping, only extraversion, openness, agreeableness, and neuroticism; and in dysfunctional coping, neuroticism, openness, and extraversion while the agreeableness trait negatively explained it. Finally, openness, conscientiousness, and extraversion significantly influenced self-efficacy. Based on the findings, a proposed action plan could help the institution deliver an efficient learning experience during the present crisis.

Keywords: Self-efficacy, Personality Traits, Coping Skills, Pandemic

Introduction

The education system in the Philippines stopped during the COVID-19 pandemic, according to UNESCO (as cited in de Guzman, 2021), around the remaining weeks of the school year 2019-2020, wherein some 24.9 million students were affected; the education system had to continue nonetheless as Leonor Briones, Secretary of the Department of Education (DepEd), stated that education must continue despite times of crisis (Department of Education, 2020, as cited in Joaquin et al., 2020); therefore, DepEd provided a solution to utilize various learning options: online learning, self-learning materials, and flexible learning, intending to deliver quality education amid the physical limitations, and among these, online learning is the one used by most Higher Education Institutions (Joaquin et al., 2020). But in consideration of the poor internet connectivity in the Philippines, this modality is not ideal for everyone. For instance, de Guzman (2021) reported that the social unevenness and the lack of resources provided difficulty to many students and teachers and that Jones (2019, as cited in Joaquin et al., 2020) mentioned that 45% of Filipinos and 74% of public schools do not have access to the internet.

Aside from the difficulty of utilizing online learning during the pandemic, psychological factors are also significant to examine. For instance, Liu et al. (2020, as cited in Talsma et al., 2020) stated that the present

pandemic is perceived as a stressor affecting significant changes in cognition, behavior, and feeling across the educational setting.

Furthermore, de Guzman (2021) mentioned that some students found studying remotely exhausting, and Joaquin et al. (2020) cited the petition of students and parents urging the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) to cancel online classes. But other students, according to Rotas and Cahapay (2021), still found hope from the trials they came across in remote learning, as they tried to communicate with relatives and friends, diverted attention to other matters to avoid stress, and motivated themselves. It may be due to the different coping skills of the students, as various research indicated that those with problem-focused coping differ in academic performance from those with emotion-focused, and dysfunctional coping. Moreover, according to Talsma et al. (2021), students amid the pandemic were possibly susceptible to adverse effects on self-efficacy. For instance, Movement for Safe, Equitable, Quality, and Relevant Education (2021, as cited in de Guzman, 2021) found that 66% of students perceived they learned less using the online learning modality.

Despite the struggle during the pandemic for all students, it is apparent that the reaction toward it varies. The presumed underlying factor behind this is stable personality traits. McCrae and Costa (as cited in Feist et al., 2018) theorized that five traits explain personality: conscientiousness, openness, extraversion,

neuroticism, and agreeableness, which every person has unique patterns that may predict other characteristics. In this case, analysis of personality traits may help understand other characteristics of students, such as coping skills and self-efficacy. Therefore, mainly focusing on online learning implementation to continue education amid the pandemic is not comprehensive. It is significant to consider as well the psychological factors: personality traits, coping skills, and self-efficacy, which may be overlooked as crucial human aspects, particularly during times of crisis, which may help provide an efficient learning experience to the students.

The research, thereupon, analyzed the predictive nature of personality traits towards coping skills and self-efficacy among Laguna State Polytechnic University college students due to the observed varying manifested difficulties and reactions among the students enrolled at the institution. It was crucial to analyze it further since the abrupt occurrence of the COVID-19 pandemic brought drastic changes in the education system, wherein literature about it was still scarce. Then, the research was a great help in providing a basis for the action plan that aimed to help the institution deliver an efficient learning experience amid the pandemic.

Methodology

The research was about analyzing the predictive nature of personality traits in terms of the other characteristics of the respondents: coping skills, and self-efficacy, through multiple linear regression analysis. Aside from that, there was no treatment provided to the respondents. Hence, among the different types of quantitative research, it was correlational research that Bhandari (2022) discussed as research that investigates relationships between variables without control and manipulation of the independent variable, which uses correlation and regression analyses. Nonetheless, it was essential to consider that correlational design was not limited to the natural association between variables. According to Sousa et al. (2007), correlational research design had three kinds: descriptive, model testing, and predictive, which the latter suited to the aim of the present research, that was, the prediction of the variance of a variable based

on the variance of another variable. Therefore, the study was predictive correlational research.

The respondents (n=1039) were from the LSPU system (Santa Cruz, Siniloan, San Pablo City, & Los Baños Campuses) wherein chosen colleges, through the use of cluster-random sampling, were as follows: 37.25% (387 respondents) from the College of Arts and Sciences; 14.05% (146 respondents) from the College of Business Management and Accountancy; 12.99% (135 respondents) from the College of Industrial Technology; 5.97% (62 respondents) from the College of Nursing and Allied Health; and 29.74% (309 respondents) from the College of Teacher Education.

In order to gauge the variables, there were three adopted questionnaires utilized. The first questionnaire was the Big Five Inventory (John, Donahue, & Kentle, 1991; John, Naumann, & Soto, 2008), which has 44 items on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = disagree strongly to 5 = agree strongly) measuring the five personality factors while items with 'R' were scored in reverse. According to John, Naumann, and Soto (2008), this instrument has a reliability of 0.83, a discriminant correlation of 0.20, and a corrected convergent validity of 0.95 with NEO-FFI of Costa and McCrae and 0.95 with Trait Descriptive Adjectives of Goldberg. The second questionnaire was the Brief COPE (Carver, 1997). It has 28 items with 14 factors containing two questions each. They were grouped into three classifications in this research: problem-focused, emotion-focused, and dysfunctional coping, based on the categorizations of Carver (1997, as cited in García et al., 2018) and Cooper et al. (2006, as cited in Abdul Rahman et al., 2021). Furthermore, Carver (1997, as cited in Su et al., 2015) reported that the internal consistency of the Brief COPE measured through Cronbach's alpha for the original subscales ranged from 0.50 (venting) to 0.90 (substance use). Measurement is through a 4-point Likert scale: 1 = I haven't been doing this at all, 2 = I've been doing this a little bit, 3 = I've been doing this a medium amount, and 4 = I've been doing this a lot.

Lastly, the third questionnaire was the New General Self-Efficacy Scale (Chen et al., 2001), which was accessible in the toolkit of Stanford SPARQ (n.d.) as part of the Measuring Mobility from Poverty (Acs et al., 2018). It has eight items, with a Likert scale, that measure how much a person believes his or her capability to achieve the goals, despite difficulties. It is a self-report test wherein the respondents will have to choose the level of agreement or disagreement towards the presented items, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree)

to 5 (strongly agree). More so, Chen et al. (2001) reported that it has high reliability and construct validity.

Results and Discussion

The following sections provided the results, interpretation, and discussion of each variable.

Table 1.1 *Level of Manifestation of Extraversion Among College Students of the LSPU System*

ITEMS	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
E1. Is talkative	3.55	Manifested
E2. Is reserved	2.32	Fairly Manifested
E3. Is full of energy	3.57	Manifested
E4. Generates a lot of enthusiasm	3.61	Manifested
E5. Tends to be quiet	2.32	Fairly Manifested
E6. Has an assertive personality	3.44	Manifested
E7. Is sometimes shy, inhibited	2.08	Fairly Manifested
E8. Is outgoing, sociable	3.34	Moderately Manifested
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.03	Moderately Manifested

Table 1.1 presented that among college students in the LSPU system amid the pandemic, the extraversion domain of personality traits had a mean of 3.03 which was interpreted as Moderately Manifested. In this domain, the item “Generates a lot of enthusiasm” had the highest mean of 3.61, among other items, which was interpreted as Manifested. While the item “Is sometimes shy, inhibited” was Fairly Manifested with the lowest mean of 2.08.

The results recommend that the extraversion trait is observable to the students of LSPU in the manner of being enthusiastic and influencing other students. For this reason, it is less likely for them to become inhibited. It is a remarkable finding that students high in extraversion continue generating excitement amid the COVID-19 pandemic. But it is important to note that they were also affected by the restrictions imposed that, according to Rettew et al. (2021), resulted in a decrease in the mood but still higher relative to those low in this trait. The research finding of Getzmann et al. (2021) could explain the maintenance of their enthusiasm. They found that extraverted individuals manage to maintain or regain social connections during the pandemic restriction by being creative in seeking substitute means to communicate, according to Iterbeke and de Witte (2021), like phone calls and other social media platforms available.

Table 1.2 *Level of Manifestation of Neuroticism Among College Students of the LSPU System*

ITEMS	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
N1. Is depressed, blue	2.99	Moderately Manifested
N2. Is relaxed, handles stress well	2.73	Moderately Manifested
N3. Can be tense	3.54	Manifested
N4. Worries a lot	3.93	Manifested
N5. Is emotionally stable, not easily upset	2.93	Moderately Manifested
N6. Can be moody	3.90	Manifested
N7. Remains calm in tense situations	2.53	Fairly Manifested
N8. Gets nervous easily	3.95	Manifested
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.31	Moderately Manifested

Table 1.2 showed that among college students in the LSPU system amid the pandemic, the neuroticism domain of personality traits had a mean of 3.31 which was interpreted as Moderately Manifested. In this domain, “Get nervous easily” was the item with the highest mean of 3.95 and was interpreted as Manifested. While the item “Remains calm in tense situations” had the lowest mean of 2.53 which was interpreted as Fairly Manifested. The result suggests that the students in the LSPU system are easily nervous, and thus remaining calm is difficult, which the COVID-19 pandemic may contribute to. According to Bhagat et al. (2019), being too emotional is associated with having prominent neuroticism. Moreover, as stated in Kroencke et al. (2020), it is this trait that individuals are manifesting more negative affect, especially amid the pandemic.

Table 1.3 *Level of Manifestation of Conscientiousness Among College Students of the LSPU System*

ITEMS	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
C1. Does a thorough job	3.66	Manifested
C2. Can be somewhat careless	2.53	Fairly Manifested
C3. Is a reliable worker	3.95	Manifested
C4. Tends to be disorganized	3.15	Moderately Manifested
C5. Tends to be lazy	2.62	Moderately Manifested
C6. Perseveres until the task is finished	3.91	Manifested
C7. Does things efficiently	3.87	Manifested
C8. Makes plans and follows through with them	3.70	Manifested
C9. Is easily distracted	2.36	Fairly Manifested
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.31	Moderately Manifested

Table 1.3 displayed that among college students in the LSPU system amid the pandemic, the conscientiousness domain of personality traits had a mean of 3.31 which was interpreted as Moderately Manifested. Specifically, the item “Is a reliable worker” had the highest mean of 3.95, which was interpreted as Manifested. But the item “Is easily distracted” only had a mean of 2.36 and was interpreted as Fairly Manifested.

The results suggest that despite studying amid the COVID-19 pandemic, the conscientiousness trait is observable to the students through being consistently good in their academics and other relevant activities,

which may buffer them from being distracted by irrelevant matters. Iterbeke and de Witte (2021) explained that students high in this trait adjusted well to the new learning experience amid the present pandemic. Because, as Jensen (2015) explained, it is due to this trait that enables students to strive for the highest possible attainment and, according to Bhagat et al. (2019), focus on the planned course content and framework.

Table 1.4 *Level of Manifestation of Agreeableness Among College Students of the LSPU System*

ITEMS	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
A1. Tends to find fault with others	3.31	Moderately Manifested
A2. Is helpful and unselfish with others	4.06	Manifested
A3. Starts quarrels with others	3.76	Manifested
A4. Has a forgiving nature	4.07	Manifested
A5. Is generally trusting	4.07	Manifested
A6. Can be cold and aloof	2.50	Fairly Manifested
A7. Is considerate and kind to almost everyone	4.09	Manifested
A8. Is sometimes rude to others	3.27	Moderately Manifested
A9. Likes to cooperate with others	3.89	Manifested
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.67	Manifested

Table 1.4 showed that among college students in the LSPU system amid the pandemic, the agreeableness domain of personality traits had a mean of 3.67 which was interpreted as Manifested. Specifically, within this domain, the item with the highest mean of 4.09 was “Is considerate and kind to almost everyone” which was interpreted as Manifested. On the contrary, the item “Can be cold and aloof” was only Fairly Manifested with a mean of 2.50.

The result infers that agreeableness is manifested in the students of LSPU by being thoughtful of other students’ feelings and needs, which surmount the rare instance of having a lack of compassion for others. In general, Graziano et al. (2007, as cited in Getzmann et al., 2021) mentioned that students high in this trait are empathic, and, according to Jensen-Campbell and Graziano (2001, as cited in Getzmann et al., 2021), exhibit a desire to maintain a good relationship. Thus, as Komarraju et al. (2011, as cited in Bhagat et al., 2019) stated, students high in this trait are more likely to interact with other students and even teachers.

Table 1.5 *Level of Manifestation of Openness Among College Students of the LSPU System*

ITEMS	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
O1. Is original, comes up with new ideas	3.81	Manifested
O2. Is curious about many different things	4.29	Highly Manifested
O3. Is ingenious, a deep thinker	3.86	Manifested
O4. Has an active imagination	4.16	Manifested
O5. Is inventive	3.30	Moderately Manifested
O6. Values artistic, aesthetic experiences	4.06	Manifested
O7. Prefers work that is routine	2.27	Fairly Manifested
O8. Likes to reflect, play with ideas	3.96	Manifested
O9. Has few artistic interests	2.36	Fairly Manifested
O10. Is sophisticated in art, music, or literature	3.68	Manifested
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.58	Manifested

Table 1.5 showed that among college students in the LSPU system amid the pandemic, the openness domain of personality traits had a mean of 3.58 which was verbally interpreted as Manifested. In this domain, specifically, the item “Is curious about many different things” had the highest mean of 4.29 which was interpreted as Highly Manifested, but the item “Prefers work that is routine” had the lowest mean of 2.27, interpreted as Fairly Manifested.

It implies that the openness trait aid in the learning experience amid the COVID-19 pandemic, as it is evident that students in the LSPU are curious about novel experiences in the learning approach brought by the said pandemic that directly opposes the possible preference for routine school activities. In line with this, Iterbeke and de Witte (2021) found that they adjust well to the sudden changes brought by the pandemic due to their characteristic of considering it as an opportunity to acquire new skills. Likewise, according to Keller and Karau (2013, as cited in Iterbeke & de Witte, 2021), they appreciate engaging in the new learning experience.

Table 2.1 *Level of Manifestation of Problem-Focused Coping Among College Students of the LSPU System*

ITEMS	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
P1. I've been concentrating my efforts on doing something about the situation I'm in.	3.26	Manifested
P2. I've been taking action to try to make the situation better.	3.34	Manifested
P3. I've been getting help and advice from other people.	2.83	Manifested
P4. I've been trying to get advice or help from other people about what to do.	2.79	Manifested
P5. I've been trying to come up with a strategy about what to do.	3.24	Manifested
P6. I've been thinking hard about what steps to take.	3.22	Manifested
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.11	Manifested

Table 2.1 showed that problem-focused coping among college students in the LSPU system was Manifested with a mean of 3.11. Specifically, the item with the highest mean of 3.34 was “I’ve been taking action to try to make the situation better,” which was interpreted as Manifested. But the item “I’ve been trying to get

advice or help from other people about what to do” had the lowest mean of 2.79 and was interpreted as Manifested.

The result implies that students in the LSPU system frequently engage in problem-focused coping when dealing with the present stressful situations by utilizing available resources to change the stressors, but asking for advice or support from other people is also a possible recourse. In line with this, Bjørndal et al. (2021) referred to this coping as an active strategy to reduce or change the underlying factor of stressful situations by modifying environmental conditions, planning, and seeking help from other individuals. Specifically, in the educational context, the latter is similar to Apker (2022), that aside from helping themselves independently, the students seek support also from peers and instructors.

Table 2.2 *Level of Manifestation of Emotion-Focused Coping Among College Students of the LSPU System*

ITEMS	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
EF1. I've been getting emotional support from others.	2.71	Manifested
EF2. I've been getting comfort and understanding from someone.	2.93	Manifested
EF3. I've been accepting the reality of the fact that it has happened.	3.36	Manifested
EF4. I've been learning to live with it.	3.27	Manifested
EF5. I've been making jokes about it.	2.89	Manifested
EF6. I've been making fun of the situation.	2.43	Fairly Manifested
EF7. I've been trying to see it in a different light, to make it seem more positive.	3.17	Manifested
EF8. I've been looking for something good in what is happening.	3.29	Manifested
EF9. I've been trying to find comfort in my religion or spiritual beliefs.	2.92	Manifested
EF10. I've been praying or meditating.	3.22	Manifested
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.02	Manifested

Table 2.2 exhibited that emotion-focused coping among college students in the LSPU system was Manifested with a mean of 3.02. Within this domain, the item “I've been accepting the reality of the fact that it has happened,” had the highest mean of 3.36 which was interpreted as Manifested. On the other hand, the item “I've been making fun of the situation” had the lowest mean of 2.43 and was interpreted as Fairly Manifested.

The result suggests that students in the LSPU amid the pandemic frequently exercise emotion-focused coping towards the present stressful situations by accepting the event has happened and seldomly may perceive them more lightly through humor. It is comparable to the research finding of Bourdige et al. (2022) that the most used coping skill that reduces stress, particularly amid the pandemic, is acceptance of it. In particular to

the educational setting, Dayagbil et al. (2021) found that students were obliged to accept the new learning experience during the present crisis, which could be supported by the fact that, in general, emotion-focused coping is most suitable in situations that are impossible to change or remove the cause of stressors (Bru, 2019, as cited in Bjørndal, 2021). Aside from this, the research of Saricali et al. (2020) may explain that when fear of COVID-19 increases engagement in humor decreases.

Table 2.3 *Level of Manifestation of Dysfunctional Coping Among College Students of the LSPU System*

ITEMS	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
D1. I've been turning to work or other activities to take my mind off things.	3.09	Manifested
D2. I've been doing something to think about it less, such as going to movies, watching TV, reading, daydreaming, sleeping, or shopping.	3.43	Manifested
D3. I've been saying to myself "this isn't real."	2.41	Fairly Manifested
D4. I've been refusing to believe that it has happened.	2.33	Fairly Manifested
D5. I've been using alcohol or other drugs to make myself feel better.	1.49	Not Manifested
D6. I've been using alcohol or other drugs to help me get through it.	1.49	Not Manifested
D7. I've been giving up trying to deal with it.	2.32	Fairly Manifested
D8. I've been giving up the attempt to cope.	2.27	Fairly Manifested
D9. I've been criticizing myself.	3.09	Manifested
D10. I've been blaming myself for things that happened.	2.80	Manifested
D11. I've been saying things to let my unpleasant feelings escape.	2.77	Manifested
D12. I've been expressing my negative feelings.	2.67	Manifested
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.51	Manifested

Table 2.3 displayed the result that dysfunctional coping among college students in the LSPU system was Manifested with a mean of 2.51. In this domain, the item with the highest mean of 3.43 was “I've been doing something to think about it less, such as going to movies, watching TV, reading, daydreaming, sleeping, or shopping,” which was interpreted as Manifested. Meanwhile, items “I've been using alcohol or other drugs to make myself feel better” and “I've been using alcohol or other drugs to help me get through it” had the lowest means of 1.49 and were interpreted as Not Manifested. The result implies that students in the LSPU system amid the COVID-19 pandemic engage with dysfunctional coping by diverting their attention to other counterproductive activities: going to movies, watching TV, reading, daydreaming, or shopping. Nonetheless, it is not expected from the students of the said institution to engage in addictive substances, like drugs or alcohol, when dealing with the stressors. Comparably, Rotas and Cahapay (2021) mentioned the stress brought by distance learning led students to cope with leisure activities. For instance, Sideridis (2008, as cited in Kwaah & Essilfie, 2017) found five common

coping skills that are observable to students: watching TV, instant messaging, internet browsing, sleeping, and resting, Nagar (2021) pointed out that these are for a solitary and therapeutic purpose to distract themselves and gain comfort amid the said pandemic. Aside from that, the research findings are similar to Kwaah and Essilfie (2017) and Bourdige et al. (2022) that substance use is the least manner for students to cope.

Table 3 Level of Self-Efficacy Among College Students of the LSPU System

ITEMS	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
S1. I will be able to achieve most of the goals that I set for myself.	4.25	Very High
S2. When facing difficult tasks, I am certain that I will accomplish them.	4.16	High
S3. In general, I think that I can obtain outcomes that are important to me.	4.26	Very High
S4. I believe I can succeed at most any endeavor to which I set my mind.	4.23	Very High
S5. I will be able to successfully overcome many challenges.	4.27	Very High
S6. I am confident that I can perform effectively on many different tasks.	4.00	High
S7. Compared to other people, I can do most tasks very well.	3.55	High
S8. Even when things are tough, I can perform quite well.	3.93	High
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	4.08	High

Table 3 displayed that among college students in the LSPU system amid the pandemic, their self-efficacy level was High with a mean of 4.08. Specifically, the item “I will be able to successfully overcome many challenges” had the highest mean of 4.27 and was interpreted as Very High. However, the lowest mean of 3.55, belonged to the item “Compared to other people, I can do most tasks very well,” but still interpreted as High. The result suggests that amid the present crisis, the students in the LSPU have a high level of self-efficacy, particularly when it comes to their triumphant outlook whenever they encounter it and believe that they perform well relative to other students. In line with this is the finding of Lopez et al. (2021) about the high self-efficacy of students as observed in their confidence to confront trials amid the present crisis. Moreover, Hayat et al. (2020) explained that they attain high achievement due to the quality of effort they exert compared to other students.

Table 4.1

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of Problem-Focused Coping and Personality Traits Among College Students of the LSPU System

PREDICTOR	ESTIMATE	SE	t	P	STAND. ESTIMATE	INTERPRETATION
Intercept	0.1688	0.1993	0.847	0.397		
N	0.0837	0.0275	3.049	0.002	0.0955	Significant
O	0.2502	0.0377	6.641	<.001	0.2011	Significant
C	0.1928	0.0344	5.597	<.001	0.1902	Significant
A	0.1230	0.0312	3.939	<.001	0.1279	Significant
E	0.2257	0.0291	7.769	<.001	0.2261	Significant

Model Fit Measures: R=0.479, R²=0.229, F=61.5, df1=5, df2=1033, p < .001
 Legend: Neuroticism (N), Openness (O), Conscientiousness (C), Agreeableness (A), Extraversion (E)

Table 4.1 showed the predictive analysis of personality traits, either singly or in combination, towards problem-focused coping. It was observed that 22.9 % of the variance in problem-focused coping was significantly explained by personality traits (R² = 0.229, F (5, 1033)= 61.5, p < 0.001). Specifically, each dimension of personality traits significantly predicted the use of problem-focused coping among the college students of LSPU system: 25% by openness (B=0.25, p < 0.001), 23% by extraversion (B=0.23, p < 0.001), 19% by conscientiousness (B=0.19, p < 0.001), 12% by agreeableness (B=0.12, p < 0.001), and only 8% by neuroticism (B=0.08, p=0.002).

It implies that personality traits both in combination and singly significantly predicted the use of problem-focused coping among the said respondents. In line with this, Agbaria and Mokh (2021) found an association between problem-focused coping and a high level of personality traits: openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, and agreeableness. Specifically, people high in these individual traits tend to manifest characteristics related to the use of problem-focused coping. People with a high openness trait tend to solve the problem, as explained by Afshar et al. (2015), and, according to Agbaria and Mokh (2021), agreeableness was positively associated with this coping. Further, Seely (2018) stated those with high conscientiousness confront stressful situations with logic rather than seek support from others, and people with high extraversion traits engage in problem-solving and planning strategies toward the stressors (Roesch et al., 2006, as cited in Agbaria & Mokh, 2021). In contrast, most of the literature established evidence about the influence of neuroticism on emotion-focused coping. Thus, this present significant finding is remarkably astounding, although there is only 8% of the variance of problem-focused coping explained by it. Among the scarce similar literature, the possible explanation for this is that of Hudek-Knezevic et al. (2005, as cited in Afshar et al., 2015), they noted that individuals high in neuroticism are often associated with maladaptive coping skills. But they could still use adaptive skills, like problem-focused coping, although ineffectively.

Table 4.2 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of Emotion-Focused Coping and Personality Traits Among College Students of the LSPU System

PREDICTOR	ESTIMATE	SE	t	p	STAND. ESTIMATE	INTERPRE TATION
Intercept	0.8419	0.1885	4.466	< .001		
N	0.0516	0.0260	1.989	0.047	0.0646	Significant
O	0.2251	0.0356	6.318	< .001	0.1983	Significant
C	0.0169	0.0326	0.520	0.603	0.0183	Not Significant
A	0.1035	0.0295	3.506	< .001	0.1180	Significant
E	0.2525	0.0275	9.191	< .001	0.2773	Significant
Model Fit Measures: R=0.415, R ² =0.172, F=42.9, df1=5, df2=1033, p < .001						Significant

Legend: Neuroticism (N), Openness (O), Conscientiousness (C), Agreeableness (A), Extraversion (E)

Table 4.2 exhibited the predictive analysis of personality traits, both singly and in combination, towards emotion-focused coping. There was 17.2 % of variance that personality traits significantly explained in emotion-focused coping ($R^2 = 0.172$, $F(5, 1033) = 42.9$, $p < 0.001$). In this domain, most of the personality traits significantly predicted the use of emotion-focused coping among the college students of LSPU system: 25% by extraversion ($B=0.25$, $p < 0.001$), 22% by openness ($B=0.22$, $p < 0.001$), 10% by agreeableness ($B=0.10$, $p < 0.001$), and 5% by neuroticism ($B=0.05$, $p=0.047$). On the other hand, conscientiousness ($B=0.02$, $p=0.603$) did not significantly predict the use of emotion-focused coping among the respondents. It implies that the use of emotion-focused coping among the college students of the LSPU system can be significantly predicted by the combined personality traits and each trait, except for conscientiousness. Recent research is in line with the findings. For instance, Panaitescu (2018) mentioned that extraversion is associated with the ability of a person to seek emotional support. Next, agreeableness, according to Agbaria and Mokh (2021), employs humor when coping with a taxing event. Likewise, they found that it is related to openness as people high with this trait accept emotions comfortably. Aside from these, it is remarkable to find that neuroticism predicts the use of adaptive emotion-focused coping. According to Smith et al. (1989, as cited in Agbaria & Mokh, 2021), this trait is positively related to adaptive emotion-focused coping: seeking emotional support, suggesting some individual differences. Lastly, only conscientiousness has no significance in predicting the emotion-focused coping among college students in the LSPU, since individuals with a high conscientiousness considerably use logic when encountering stressors (Seely, 2018).

Table 4.3 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of Dysfunctional Coping and Personality Traits Among

College Students of the LSPU System

PREDICTOR	ESTIMATE	SE	t	p	STAND. ESTIMATE	INTERPRE TATION
Intercept	1.4283	0.1924	7.42	< .001		
N	0.2426	0.0265	9.15	< .001	0.2924	Significant
O	0.1805	0.0364	4.96	< .001	0.1533	Significant
C	-0.0493	0.0332	-1.48	0.138	-0.0515	Not Significant
A	-0.2067	0.0301	-6.86	< .001	-0.2273	Significant
E	0.1846	0.0280	6.58	< .001	0.1954	Significant
Model Fit Measures: R=0.445, R ² =0.198, F=51.5, df1=5, df2=1033, p < .001						Significant

Legend: Neuroticism (N), Openness (O), Conscientiousness (C), Agreeableness (A), Extraversion (E)

Table 4.3 exhibited the predictive analysis of personality traits, both singly and in combination, towards dysfunctional coping. The personality traits, in combination, significantly explained 19.8% of the variance in dysfunctional coping ($R^2 = 0.198$, $F(5, 1033) = 51.1$, $p < 0.001$). Individually, most of the personality traits significantly predicted the use of dysfunctional coping among the college students of LSPU system: 24% by neuroticism ($B=0.24$, $p < 0.001$), 18% by openness ($B=0.18$, $p < 0.001$), and 18% by extraversion ($B=0.18$, $p < 0.001$). But agreeableness ($B= -0.21$, $p < 0.001$) predicted negatively the engagement of the respondents with dysfunctional coping, particularly 21% of its variance. Finally, conscientiousness ($B = -0.05$, $p = 0.138$) did not significantly predict the use of dysfunctional coping among the respondents. The result suggests that personality traits, as a group, significantly predicted dysfunctional coping. Individually, neuroticism, openness, and extraversion significantly predicted it. But agreeableness could negatively predict the use of dysfunctional coping. Lastly, conscientiousness does not significantly predict the said coping skill.

In connection to these, Getzmann et al. (2021) implied that neuroticism is associated with maladaptive or dysfunctional coping: avoidance, venting, and hostility while Boyes and French (2010, as cited in Agbaria & Mokh, 2021) included as well the substance use, behavioral disengagement, and self-blame. The significance of openness towards dysfunctional coping is due to, as explained by Lee-Baggeley et al. (2005, as cited in Seely, 2018), their capability to adapt and cope in a creative manner. Moreover, according to Pilch et al. (2021), extraversion is significant due to its possible inclination to use avoidance or wishful thinking behavior. But the negative association of agreeableness with the utilization of dysfunctional coping is similar to that of Hengartner et al. (2017, as cited in Agbaria & Mokh, 2021) that this trait is negatively associated with impulsive behaviors manifested in some dysfunctional manner of coping, like substance use. Because, people with this trait are

altruistic, trustful, and useful that is consistent with the nature of more adaptive coping strategies (Agbaria & Mokh, 2021). Finally, individuals with prominent conscientiousness traits do not usually utilize dysfunctional coping (Leszko et al., 2020) because of being dependable, determined, and committed people (Scigala et al., 2020).

Table 5 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of Self- Efficacy and Personality Traits Among College Students of the LSPU System

PREDICTOR	ESTIMATE	SE	t	P	STAND. ESTIMATE	INTERPRETATION
Intercept	0.61912	0.2342	2.643	0.008		
N	0.00927	0.0322	0.287	0.774	0.00869	Not Significant
O	0.39513	0.0443	8.928	< 0.001	0.26086	Significant
C	0.31609	0.0405	7.814	< 0.001	0.25631	Significant
A	0.06068	0.0367	1.654	0.098	0.05186	Not Significant
E	0.24855	0.0341	7.282	< 0.001	0.20456	Significant
Model Fit Measures: R=0.531, R ² =0.282, F=81.3, df1=5, df2=1033, p < .001						Significant

Legend: Neuroticism (N), Openness (O), Conscientiousness (C), Agreeableness (A), Extraversion (E)

Table 5 showed the predictive analysis of personality traits, both singly and in combination, towards self-efficacy. The personality traits, in combination, significantly explained 28.2% of the variance in self-efficacy ($R^2 = 0.282$, $F(5, 1033) = 81.3$, $p < 0.001$). Likewise, three personality traits significantly predicted the variance of self-efficacy among the college students of LSPU system: 40% by openness ($B=0.40$, $p < 0.001$), 32% by conscientiousness ($B=0.32$, $p < 0.001$), and 25% by extraversion ($B=0.25$, $p < 0.001$). However, both neuroticism ($B=0.01$, $p = 0.774$) and agreeableness ($B=0.06$, $p < 0.098$) did not significantly predict the self-efficacy of the respondents.

In this result, personality traits significantly predict self-efficacy in combination and singly: openness, conscientiousness, and extraversion, among college students in the LSPU system during the COVID-19 pandemic. Similar to this is the conclusion of Zakiei et al. (2020) that personality traits influence self-efficacy. The three personality traits: openness, conscientiousness, and extraversion, significantly influence due to their manifested characteristics. First, according to Zakiei et al. (2020), individuals prominent with openness traits tend to manage tasks effectively and to increase efforts that support them to attain self-efficacy. Also, Redmond (2010, as cited in Zakiei et al., 2020) reported that this trait provided a tendency to become less disappointed even if they experienced an unexpected outcome. Second, extraversion's behavioral manifestation helped in building self-efficacy based on Redmond (2010, as

cited in Zakiei et al., 2020) by receiving encouragement from others and, according to Bandura (1997, as cited in Zakiei, 2020), by expressing feelings and thoughts. Third, due to the behavioral presentation of conscientiousness, individuals high in this trait were more likely to set realistic goals and believe in their selves resulting in the growth of self-efficacy (Zakiei et al., 2020). On the other hand, Ambiel and Noronha (2016) found neuroticism is not a significant predictor of self-efficacy, and Abood et al. (2020) stated that agreeableness does not significantly associate with the latter.

Conclusion

The following implications were based on the findings regarding the personality traits, coping skills, and self-efficacy among the college students of the LSPU system amid the COVID-19 pandemic: Openness is manifested through their curiosity about the novel experiences in the learning approach brought by the pandemic, which directly opposes the possible preference for routine school activities. Second, conscientiousness is observable to the students in a manner of being consistently good in their academics and other relevant activities, which may buffer them from being distracted by irrelevant matters. Third, the extraversion trait is apparent to the students of LSPU in being enthusiastic and influencing other students even amid the present crisis, and it is less likely for them to become shy. Fourth, the manifestation of agreeableness among the respondents is being thoughtful of other students' feelings and needs, which surmount the rare instance of having a lack of compassion for others. Nonetheless, the fifth personality trait, neuroticism, is manifested by easily getting nervous, making it difficult to keep calm.

In terms of coping skills, problem-focused coping is observed by utilizing available resources to change the stressors, yet asking for advice or support from other people is also a possible resort. Emotion-focused coping is also manifested by accepting an event that has happened and seldomly may perceive stressful situations more lightly through humor. Finally, students in the LSPU system amid the pandemic engage as well in dysfunctional coping by diverting their attention to other counterproductive activities. But it is not expected from the students of the said institution to engage in addictive substances when dealing with the stressors. Furthermore, personality traits significantly predict, in combination, the use of problem-focused, emotion-focused, and dysfunctional coping among the college students of LSPU amid the

pandemic. Specifically, all personality traits: openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism significantly predict problem-focused coping. Only conscientiousness does not significantly predict emotion-focused and dysfunctional coping. Although, agreeableness negatively predicts the latter coping.

Aside from these, students in the LSPU system have a high level of self-efficacy despite the COVID-19 pandemic, especially when it comes to their positive outlook when they encounter challenges and believe that they perform well relative to other students. More so, personality traits significantly predict self-efficacy in combination and singly: openness, conscientiousness, and extraversion, among college students in the LSPU system during the COVID-19 pandemic. But the other traits: neuroticism and agreeableness, are not significant predictors of self-efficacy.

Finally, the research findings served as the basis for the proposed action plan that aims to support the implementation of quality learning experiences among the college students of the LSPU system amid the present crisis by teaching them how to face the difficulties with learned techniques of keeping calm through mindfulness exercises and journal: expressive and gratitude types;

. Also, utilize an adapted or culturally appropriate research instrument and broaden the respondents aside from college students to better generalize the results about the students in the Philippines. Finally, the institution may utilize the recommended action, as it

could help provide an efficient learning experience in the present crisis.

References

- Acs, G., Maitreyi, A., Conner, A.L., Markus, H.R., Patel, N.G., Lyons-Padilla, S., & Eberhardt, J.L. (2018, April). *Measuring Mobility from Poverty*. Stanford SPARQtools.
- Carver, C. S. (1997). You want to measure coping but your protocol's too long: Consider the Brief COPE. *International Journal of Behavioral Medicine*, 4, 92-100
- Chen, G., Gully, S. M., & Eden, D. (2001). Validation of a New General Self-Efficacy Scale. *Organizational Research Methods*, 4(1), 62-83.
- John, O. P., Donahue, E. M., & Kentle, R. L. (1991). *The Big Five Inventory--Versions 4a and 54*. Berkeley, CA: University of California, Berkeley, Institute of Personality and Social Research.
- John, O. P., Naumann, L. P., & Soto, C. J. (2008). Paradigm Shift to the Integrative Big-Five Trait Taxonomy: History, Measurement, and Conceptual Issues. In O. P. John, R. W. Robins, & L. A. Pervin (Eds.), *Handbook of personality: Theory and research* (pp. 114-158). New York, NY: Guilford Press.
- Stanford SPARQ. (n.d.). *New General Self-Efficacy Scale*. Stanford SPARQtools.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Dhon Jheriko Enrico

Laguna College of Business and Arts
Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines